

One corpus-based semantic model, many semantic tasks

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1. Introduction

The past 20 years have seen the birth of many systems that learn aspects of semantics from patterns of co-occurrence in naturally occurring data, mostly in the form of large scale linguistic corpora. *Relation extraction* algorithms (Hearst, 1992; Banko et al., 2007) look for pairs that instantiate a certain relation type, for example the *is-a* relation (cars are vehicles, wolves are mammals, ...). *Word space models* (Sahlgren, 2006) measure taxonomic similarity among concepts by the degree to which they tend to share similar contexts. These models achieve very good results in tasks such as synonym identification and categorization. Finally, corpus-based semantics recently began to tackle aspects of *semantic compositionality*, the ability to (recursively) create composite meanings from simpler ones (Kintsch, 2001; Mitchell and Lapata, 2008). Compositionality is a complex phenomenon, but one particularly important facet of it pertains to compatibility constraints on composition (Resnik, 1996; Erk, 2007): Even if you have not heard either sentence before, *I killed a kangaroo* makes more sense than *I killed a book*.

I argue that one of the most important goals for corpus-based semantics in the next few years is to develop a common corpus-derived model that can be tuned to perform all these tasks and more. This is a necessary step both in theoretical terms (human semantic knowledge is flexible enough to allow us to perform all these tasks) and for practical purposes (embedding semantic knowledge in applications should be a matter of tuning an existing resource to a new task, and it should not require going back to a corpus and training a new ad-hoc system each time).

2. Semantic models as target+type+feature tuples

All the tasks sketched above can indeed be performed by a model that stores corpus-based information as a weighted list of *target+type+feature* tuples. The target list will typically be extracted from the corpus according to some criterion (e.g., the top N words, the top N words filtered by part-of-speech, etc.). Types are strings that cue the relation that exists between the target and the feature. For example, they can be dependency paths extracted from a parse of the corpus, or (generalizations of) lexico-syntactic patterns. The features are words (or multi-word elements) that are syntagmatically linked to the targets by the relevant type (e.g., the verb *to eat* might be a feature of the target

apple, with relation type *obj*). Finally, weighting is based on standard statistical measures such as Mutual Information or Log-Likelihood Ratio (Evert, 2004), that mark the degree of syntagmatic association between the elements of a tuple.

3. Examples

While any model equipped with the relevant information would do, I present here examples from StruDEL (Baroni et al., submitted), a fully unsupervised model trained on a large corpus of English Web pages (about 2 billion tokens). Table 1 reports the top 10 tuples extracted by StruDEL for the targets *book* and *tiger* (using Log-Likelihood Ratio weighting).

Given these tuples, the task of relation extraction is rather straightforward. We can identify, either by hand or using standard weakly supervised methods, types that instantiate the relation of interest, and look for target-feature pairs that occur in highly weighted tuples with the extracted types. For example, it is pretty clear from the examples in Table 1 that we could use the type *T in F* (among others) to harvest features that instantiate the location relation. In Baroni et al. (submitted) we show that this approach compares favorably against a state-of-the-art ad-hoc relation extraction algorithm, when searching for locations and functions.

Taxonomic similarity, such as has been traditionally extracted by word space models, can be computed by building a matrix whose rows are the targets, the columns (dimensions) are type+feature pairs, and the tuple weights fill the corresponding cells (e.g., the *book* vector will have a *T for F: reader-n* dimension with value 5024.4). Cosines or other standard measures of similarity can be computed from this matrix. Table 2 shows the nearest neighbours of *book* and *tiger* collected in this way. As these examples suggest, and as we confirmed quantitatively in Baroni et al. (submitted), vectors constructed from type-feature dimensions can do very well in tasks requiring information about taxonomic similarity.

For the final task, modeling compatibility restrictions on compositionality, I focus on the classic problem of checking whether a noun is appropriate to fill a verbal argument slot. First, I extract the targets (nouns) occurring in the top N (in my experiments: 30) tuples that contain the verb of interest as feature and a type marking the argument relation of interest. I call these nouns the “model set” for the slot. I then compute the similarity of other nouns to the centroid

<i>book</i>			<i>tiger</i>		
<i>type</i>	<i>feature</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>type</i>	<i>feature</i>	<i>weight</i>
T for F	reader-n	5024.4	T in F	jungle-n	183.5
T by F	author-n	4406.7	T in F	zoo-n	164.4
obj	read-v	4314.3	F on T	lion-n	103.3
T in F	library-n	3925.1	F by T	maul-v	101.4
F in T	chapter-n	3303.4	subj	kill-v	93.6
obj	write-v	2919.0	F on T	stripe-n	90.1
subj	publish-v	2454.5	T in F	cage-n	83.3
T from F	publisher-n	2417.2	F such as T	specie-n	77.3
F of T	page-n	1836.4	F for T	habitat-n	73.3
T on F	subject-n	1422.4	T from F	extinction-n	73.7

Table 1: Top ranked tuples for targets *book* and *tiger*

<i>book</i>		<i>tiger</i>	
<i>neighbour</i>	<i>cosine</i>	<i>neighbour</i>	<i>cosine</i>
story	0.27	gorilla	0.33
magazine	0.25	elephant	0.29
photograph	0.08	bear	0.28
wrapper	0.07	lion	0.28
tape	0.06	fox	0.24
disc	0.05	monkey	0.21
painting	0.03	leopard	0.20
table	0.03	wolf	0.17
tool	0.03	rhino	0.17
library	0.02	penguin	0.16

Table 2: Nearest neighbours of books and tigers

<i>object</i>		<i>instrument</i>	
<i>noun</i>	<i>cosine</i>	<i>noun</i>	<i>cosine</i>
kangaroo	0.52	heroin	0.33
snake	0.29	stone	0.31
person	0.27	antibiotic	0.30
fun	0.22	brick	0.25
robot	0.15	hammer	0.23
flower	0.12	sympathy	0.14
stone	0.10	flower	0.14
lake	0.09	smile	0.13
book	0.08	person	0.12
graduation	0.08	graduation	0.12

Table 3: Potential object and instrumental arguments of *to kill*

of the model set, using the same vector representation described above. The prediction is that only nouns compatible with the slot will have high similarity to the model set (this is similar to the method of Erk, 2007, but I start from the tuples already stored in the model, rather than harvesting ad-hoc data from the corpus).

Results for the object and “instrumental” (*with*) slots of the verb *to kill* and 10 test items (none of them in the respective model set) are reported in table 3. With the exception of the relatively high position of *fun* as an object, the ranking reflects my semantic compatibility intuitions almost perfectly.

4. Conclusion

Given the impressive growth of corpus-based semantics in recent years, it is time to ask to what extent different tasks that have been tackled with ad-hoc methods can be integrated into a single system. There are good reasons to think that this integration can be straightforward, and that the core format in which corpus-derived information should be stored is as weighted target+type+feature tuples.

5. References

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